

Non Performing Financing (NPF) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Non Performing Financing (NPF) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the NPF ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the NPF ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the NPF ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 576 journal publications regarding the NPF ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the NPF ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 178 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 32 topics around the influence of the NPF ratio and 49 topics about the determinants of the NPF ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around NPF ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Non Performing Financing (NPF); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

The NPF ratio is a measure to measure credit quality or a bank's ability to manage credit risk. This ratio is calculated by dividing the total loans that the borrower cannot pay or that are overdue for more than 90 days by the total bank loans. The higher the NPF ratio, the greater the credit risk faced by the bank, because the more loans the borrower cannot repay. In the period before the COVID-19 pandemic, the NPF ratio at most banks in Indonesia was relatively low, namely below 5%. However, in 2020, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic caused an increase in the number of debtors who had difficulty repaying loans, resulting in an increase in the NPF ratio in banks in Indonesia. The Indonesian government then took action to reduce the impact of the pandemic, including by providing credit restructuring relaxation (Usy et al., 2017) .

Credit restructuring is one way that banks can reduce their credit risk. Credit restructuring is a process in which banks provide payment relief to borrowers experiencing financial difficulties so that the borrower can repay the loan. Payment relief can take the form of extending payment terms, reducing interest rates, or delaying interest payments. Apart from restructuring credit, banks can also add reserves for credit losses. Credit loss reserves are reserves

created by banks to anticipate losses that may occur due to credit that cannot be repaid by the borrower. These reserves can be used to cover losses arising from credit risks faced by the bank. The development of the NPF ratio in banks in Indonesia is an important thing to monitor, because this ratio is an indicator of a bank's financial health. If the NPF ratio is getting higher, the bank needs to take action to reduce its credit risk, such as by restructuring credit or adding reserves for credit losses. This is important to do to maintain the bank's financial health and to minimize risks to the financial system as a whole (Abdillah, 2020) .

Several studies regarding NPF in banking include: first, research that analyzes the factors that influence the level of NPF in banking in Indonesia. The results of this research show that factors such as interest rates, inflation and economic growth influence the NPF level in banking in Indonesia (Nurjamil, 2021) . Second, research that analyzes the factors that influence the NPF level in Islamic banking in Indonesia. The results of this research show that interest rates, economic growth, and bank capital structure influence the NPF level in Islamic banking in Indonesia (Fhadilah, 2020) . Third, research that analyzes the influence of NPF on bank performance in sharia and conventional banking in Indonesia. The results of this research show that NPF has a negative effect on bank performance in sharia and conventional banking in Indonesia (Tsanja, 2023) . Fourth, research analyzing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on NPF levels in banking in Indonesia. The results of this research show that the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on increasing the NPF level in banks in Indonesia (Sonjaya, 2016) . These studies provide a deeper understanding of the factors that influence NPF levels in banks in Indonesia as well as the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on NPF levels in banks in Indonesia. These studies can be a reference for banks and regulators in taking action to reduce credit risk and maintain the bank's financial health in the future.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding NPF in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding NPF. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research NPF matters. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the NPF ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Non Performing Financing (NPF) is a term used in sharia banking to describe credit or financing that has matured and its payment obligations cannot be fulfilled by the customer or borrowing party. In another sense, NPF is financing that cannot be repaid on time and has passed the predetermined payment deadline. If a customer experiences NPF, sharia banking will experience losses because the funds provided cannot be returned properly. Therefore, Islamic banks have strict policies and procedures in evaluating credit risk and minimizing NPF risk. One of the efforts made by sharia banks is to

monitor and supervise customers so that they can take appropriate action if an NPF risk occurs. (Zainul, 2019) .

Bibliometric studies are Quantitative analysis method to evaluate academic and scientific performance through quantitative measurement and analysis of scientific publications. Bibliometric studies aim to identify trends, patterns and impact of scientific publications in a particular scientific discipline or research area. This method uses statistical techniques and tools to collect, measure, and analyze data related to scientific publications such as the number of articles, authors, institutional affiliations, keywords, as well as citation frequency and academic impact. This data can then be used to compare academic and scientific performance between individuals, institutions, or countries, as well as identify new and important research trends and patterns within a scientific discipline. Bibliometric studies are widely used in scientific research, institutional decision making, and assessing the quality and relevance of scientific publications. By using bibliometric studies, researchers can understand research trends and identify knowledge gaps within a scientific discipline, thereby helping in the development of better and more effective research strategies. (Dubyna et al., 2022) .

VOSviewer is a free software used in bibliometric studies and network analysis. This software is designed to help analyze scientific publication data by visualizing the relationship between various elements such as authors, keywords, journals, institutional affiliations, etc. in the form of graphs and diagrams. VOSviewer is capable of analyzing and visualizing data generated from a variety of sources, including publication databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar. In bibliometric analysis, VOSviewer is often used to map and analyze citation networks between scientific publications, which can provide insight into the relationships and influence between authors, institutions, research topics, etc. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce visualizations that are interactive and easy to understand, making it easier for researchers to understand the relationships between the elements under study. Apart from that, VOSviewer also provides various analysis features, such as clustering, co-occurrence analysis, and network analysis, which can help researchers identify research trends and map related research areas (van Eck NJ, 2022) .

Studies Library Research is a systematic research method for identifying, evaluating, and synthesizing literature or information sources related to a particular research topic or problem. This method can be used to collect and examine information from various sources, including journal articles, books, reports, and other documents, related to the topic under study. A Library Research study aims to reorganize knowledge that has been collected from various sources of information, then compare, categorize, and evaluate the literature critically. This method can also help researchers identify knowledge gaps and future research directions, as well as assess the quality and validity of information sources used in research. In the Library Research study process, researchers must carry out a comprehensive and systematic search for information, using keywords that are relevant to the research topic. After that, the researcher will read and evaluate the literature found to identify relevant and important information to add to the report or research article. This process must be carried out carefully and objectively, and involves a process of validating and testing the credibility of the information found. Mapping Research Topics using Library Research are an important research method in many scientific disciplines, because they can help strengthen research

arguments and conclusions and provide a basis for further research (El-Halaby et al., 2021) .

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Mapping Research Topics using Library Research. The research object is Non Performing Financing (NPF). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on NPF in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Non Performing Financing " and " NPF" throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding NPF using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around NPF using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around NPF using a Library Research study (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications Regarding Non Performing Financing (NPF) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 576 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2009 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding NPF by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2009	2	2018	46
2012	4	2019	91
2013	3	2020	87
2014	22	2021	128
2015	20	2022	88
2016	31	2023	15
2017	39		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

bus, business, covid, customer, data collection technique, determinant, determinant, development, exchange rate, external factor, GDP, gross domestic product, growth, indicator, Indonesia, inflation, inflation variable, internal factor, interview, Islamic banking, January, level, loan, macroeconomic variable, management, pandemic, influence of inflation, sharia banking, performance, performing finance, policy, principle, problematic financing, quality, quantitative approach, rate, relationship, research data/sample, risk, sbis, sharia banking, significant impact/influence, square, term, time series data.

- Cluster 3, consists of 38 topic items, namely: assets, sharia banks, sharia commercial banks, capital adequacy ratio, car, third party funds, panel data, dependent variable, deposit ratio, deposits, equity, evIEWS, fdr, financing, methods analysis, net operating margin, nom, non-performing margin, nom, non-performing financing, npf, oer, financial services authority, mudharabah financing, influence of capital adequacy ratio, influence of third party funds, influence of financing, performing financing, purposive sampling, ratio, return, roa, roe, spss, tbk, data analysis techniques, test, f test, t test.
- Cluster 4, consists of 20 topic items, namely: annual report, bopo, company, cost, data analysis method, financial ratio, financial services authority, financial statement, income, independent variable, insignificant effect, operating income, operational costs, panel data, path analysis, quarterly financing report, bank sharia, significant negative/positive effect, total assets.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Non-Performing Financing (NPF) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 32 influences of NPF on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Operational Costs Operational Income/BOPO. NPF can increase BOPO because banks have to incur additional costs to manage and collect back problematic financing. These costs include legal fees, court costs, collection costs, and other costs associated with recovering problematic financing. In the long term, a high NPF can affect bank profitability and the bank's ability to reduce BOPO (Emiliani et al., 2023) .

(2) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. CAR is a ratio used to measure banking ability to bear credit risk. A high NPF can reduce CAR because banks have to allocate additional capital to handle higher credit risk. This can cause banks to become more vulnerable to financial risks and limit their ability to provide new credit (Budianto, 2023) .

(3) Debt Financing. A high NPF can affect banks' access to financing sources because banks may have difficulty getting funds from financial markets or investors. This can limit the bank's ability to offer new credit and affect the bank's ability to develop business (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(4) Earnings Management. NPF can influence bank earnings management practices because banks may try to hide NPF from investors or regulators. This can cause banks to carry out earnings management practices such as underestimating NPF or increasing loss reserves to compensate for high NPF. Earnings management practices like this can endanger the long-term financial health of banks (Budianto et al., 2023) .

(5) Efficiency. A high NPF can affect the efficiency of banking operations because banks have to incur additional costs to manage and recover problematic financing. This can reduce bank efficiency and increase operational costs. In the long term, a high NPF can affect bank profitability and the bank's ability to improve operational efficiency (Gozali et al., 2023) .

(6) Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR. A high NPF can affect FDR because banks may experience a decrease in deposits from customers due to the bank's inability to return problematic financing. This can cause the FDR to become unbalanced and banks may need to look for alternative sources of financing such as short-term loans from financial markets or investors (Rofika et al., 2023) .

(7) Financial Sustainability Ratio /FSR. A high NPF can affect FSR as banks may have difficulty meeting minimum capital requirements set by regulatory authorities. This can reduce the bank's financial sustainability and result in the risk of bankruptcy. Banks may need to increase capital by looking for new investors or by selling assets to increase liquidity (Febrian & Budianto, 2023) .

(8) Financing of Natural Uncertainty Contract /NUC. NPFs may influence natural uncertainty contract (NUC) financing as banks may be more cautious in providing this type of financing due to the higher risk. This can limit the bank's ability to offer new products and services which can affect business growth and bank profitability (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(9) Zakat compliance. NPF can affect bank asset ownership and affect the bank's obligation to pay zakat. Banks may need to bear higher zakat costs if their NPF is high, which can affect the bank's financial performance and profitability. Therefore, a high NPF can affect the level of bank zakat compliance (Rohmah et al., 2023) .

(10) Financial performance. A high NPF can affect a bank's financial performance because the bank must allocate more funds to handle higher credit risks and costs associated with collecting NPF. This can reduce bank profitability and the bank's ability to improve financial performance (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(11) Company profits. A high NPF can affect bank company profits because banks have to incur additional costs to collect back problematic financing. This can reduce the bank's net profit and limit the bank's ability to pay dividends to shareholders (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(12) Murabahah Margin. A high NPF can affect a bank's murabahah margin because the bank may need to set a higher margin on new financing to offset the high NPF. This can affect the bank's competitiveness in the market and affect the bank's ability to attract new customers or retain old customers (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(13) Net Operating Margin /NOM. A high NPF can affect a bank's NOM because the bank must allocate more funds to handle the higher credit risk and costs associated with collecting NPF. This can reduce bank profitability and the bank's ability to increase NOM (Zahro et al., 2023) .

(14) Company value. A high NPF can affect a bank's corporate value because NPF can affect a bank's financial performance and profitability. This can affect bank share prices and the company's overall market value (Shalsabila et al., 2023) .

(15) Distribution of Murabahah, Mudharabah, Musyarakah financing. A high NPF can affect the distribution of bank financing because banks may need to be more careful in providing new financing. This can limit the bank's ability

to offer new products and services which can affect business growth and bank profitability (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(16) Financing the primary, secondary and tertiary economic sectors. A high NPF can reduce the bank's ability to provide financing to the economic sector. This is because banks have to allocate more funds to handle problematic financing. Apart from that, banks can also be more selective in providing financing, especially in sectors that are considered riskier (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(17) Development of sharia banking. A high NPF can influence the growth of sharia banking. This is because Islamic banks tend to depend more on financing than deposits. If Islamic banks experience high NPFs, then they must look for new sources of financing to replace funds tied to problematic financing (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(18) Determination of the profit sharing ratio. A high NPF can influence the determination of the profit sharing ratio for financing carried out by Islamic banks. This is because Islamic banks must compensate for the risks taken on problematic financing by increasing the profit sharing ratio on other financing (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(19) Financing portion. A high NPF can affect the portion of financing in certain sectors. This is because banks will tend to limit financing to sectors that are considered riskier, while increasing financing in sectors that are considered safer (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(20) Asset growth. A high NPF can hamper the growth of bank assets because the bank must allocate larger funds to handle problematic financing and carry out recovery efforts. This can reduce the bank's ability to provide new financing and hinder the growth of the bank's business (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

(21) Fraud disclosure. A high NPF can influence the disclosure of fraud in banking. This is because there is a possibility that banks will improve their financial reports by hiding the NPF or transferring it to another institution. This can affect customer and investor confidence in banks and the financial market as a whole (Rahmawati et al., 2023) .

(22) Profit Expense Ratio /PER. A high NPF can affect PER in banking. This is because banks have to incur additional costs to handle problematic financing. This can reduce bank profitability and increase PER (Fitriawati et al., 2023) .

(23) Return On Assets /ROA. A high NPF can affect ROA in banking. This is because banks have to bear losses due to problematic financing, which can reduce bank revenues and profits. This can reduce the bank's ROA and affect the bank's overall financial performance.

(24) Return On Equity /ROE. NPF can reduce ROE because banks have to hold reserves to cover losses caused by bad loans. This reduces net profit which can be used to pay dividends or increase bank equity. Apart from that, NPF can also affect a bank's performance and its credibility in the eyes of investors, which can have a negative impact on share prices.

(25) Return for Deposit /RfD Result. NPF can also affect RfD, because banks may need to increase deposit interest rates to attract funds from customers and maintain sufficient liquidity. This can increase bank funding costs, which can reduce RfDs.

(26) Stock returns. The effect of NPF on stock returns can vary depending on other factors such as stock market conditions, the bank's overall financial performance, and investors' perceptions of the bank's future prospects.

Although NPF can influence stock prices, the stock market's reaction to NPF can vary.

(27) Liquidity risk. NPF can increase liquidity risk in banking because banks may need to sell assets or take out loans to meet liquidity needs. This could increase funding costs and reduce the bank's ability to finance new credit, which could have a negative impact on ROE and RfD. Apart from that, increasing liquidity needs can also worsen the bank's financial condition if not handled properly.

(28) Stability of sharia banking. NPF can reduce the stability of Islamic banking because banks have to hold reserves to cover losses caused by bad loans. This can reduce the bank's ability to provide new financing and worsen the bank's financial condition if not handled properly. Apart from that, NPF can also affect public confidence in sharia banking as a whole, which can have a negative impact on the stability of the sharia banking sector.

(29) Profit sharing rate on Mudharabah deposits. NPF can affect the level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits because banks may need to increase deposit interest rates to attract funds from customers and maintain sufficient liquidity. This can increase bank funding costs and reduce the profit sharing rate on Mudharabah deposits.

(30) Liquidity level. NPF can affect the level of liquidity in Islamic banking because banks may need to sell assets or take out loans to meet liquidity needs. This could increase funding costs and reduce banks' ability to finance new credit, which could have a negative impact on the stability of Islamic banking.

(31) Total assets. NPF can affect total assets in Islamic banking because banks may need to sell assets or hold reserves to cover losses caused by bad loans. This can reduce the bank's total assets and worsen the bank's financial condition if not handled properly.

(32) Volume of financing. NPF can affect the volume of financing in sharia banking because banks may need to withhold new financing to cover losses caused by bad credit. This can affect the growth of the bank's business and worsen the bank's financial condition if not handled properly.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinant Variables of Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 50 NPF determinant variables in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Allocation of zakat funds. The allocation of zakat funds can affect the NPF in banking because zakat funds can be used to provide financing to customers who are unable to pay in full or are experiencing financial difficulties. In this way, banks can reduce NPF risk because customers who receive financing can pay it back.

(2) Operational Costs Operational Income/BOPO. Operational costs can affect NPF in banks because the higher the BOPO, the greater the NPF risk faced by banks. This is because the greater the BOPO, the smaller the profits generated by banks. As a result, banks become less liquid and less able to bear the risk of bad financing.

(3) BI Rate. The BI Rate can influence the NPF in banking because the BI Rate is an interest rate set by Bank Indonesia as a reference for banks in determining credit interest rates. The higher the BI Rate, the higher the credit

interest rates offered by banks. This can result in customers having difficulty paying back loans, thereby increasing NPF risk.

(4) Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR. CAR can influence NPF in banks because CAR shows how much capital a bank has to bear credit risks that may arise. The higher the CAR, the greater the banking ability to bear credit risk. Conversely, if CAR is low, banks become less liquid and less able to bear the credit risks that arise, thereby increasing NPF risk.

(5) Current Ratio. Current Ratio is a ratio that shows a bank's ability to fulfill its short-term obligations using current assets. The higher the Current Ratio, the greater the bank's ability to bear NPF risk, because the bank has sufficient liquidity to pay its obligations.

(6) Covid-19. Covid-19 can affect NPF in banking because this pandemic has had a significant economic impact, including on the banking sector. The spread of the virus and various restrictions imposed by the government have resulted in decreased demand and slow economic growth, which has an impact on customers' ability to repay their credit, thereby increasing NPF risk.

(7) Third Party Funds/DPK. DPK can influence NPF in banking because the higher the DPK, the greater the bank's ability to distribute credit, thereby reducing NPF risk. This is because the higher the DPK, the more funds available to be given to customers who need financing.

(8) Diversification of sectoral financing. Sectoral financing diversification can affect NPF in banking because banks can minimize NPF risk by spreading financing risk across different sectors. By diversifying sectoral financing, banks can minimize financing risks in certain sectors that are experiencing a decline.

(9) Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR. FDR is the ratio between the total financing provided by the bank and the amount of third party funds (deposits) collected by the bank. The higher the FDR, the greater the bank's risk to liquidity and the bank's ability to manage credit risk becomes more difficult. If the FDR is too high, banks can rely too much on external funding which is relatively expensive and risky, thereby increasing NPF risk. However, an FDR that is too low can also limit the bank's ability to provide financing, thereby reducing the bank's income and business growth.

(10) Financing Growth. High financing growth can expand the bank's customer base, increase revenue and strengthen the bank's position in the market. However, financing growth that is too fast can also increase credit risk and liquidity risk, thereby increasing NPF risk. Therefore, banks need to ensure that financing growth is carried out in a prudent and controlled manner to avoid misuse and decline in credit quality.

(11) Financing Scheme Effect. Financing schemes can influence credit risk and NPF risk. For example, financing schemes with inadequate collateral or loose financing policies can increase credit risk and NPF risk. On the other hand, an adequate and tight financing scheme can help minimize credit risk and NPF risk.

(12) Gross Domestic Product /GDP. Strong economic growth can improve bank financial performance, increase borrowers' ability to repay financing, and reduce credit risk. However, an economic slowdown or recession can increase credit risk and NPF risk, because there is a decrease in income and the borrower's ability to repay financing.

(13) Good Corporate Governance /GCG. Good governance practices can help banks better manage credit risk and minimize NPF risk. GCG ensures that banks take preventive measures against credit risk such as establishing credit committees, internal and external audits, and regular risk evaluations. In

addition, GCG can help ensure that banks have strict policies in providing credit, implement collective action against debtors in arrears, and manage credit risk effectively.

(14) Hybrid Contract for restructuring. Hybrid contracts can help banks to restructure problematic loans and avoid credit failures. A hybrid contract is a form of contract that combines different types of contracts, for example between debt contracts and equity contracts. Hybrid contracts can allow banks to earn more profits in the long term and provide flexibility in handling problem loans.

(15) Guarantee. Providing guarantees or collateral can help minimize credit risk and NPF risk. Collateral in the form of assets used as collateral can provide certainty regarding credit repayment, thereby reducing the credit risk faced by the bank. The guarantee provided must also be adjusted to the type of credit and risks faced by the bank. In the event that the debtor fails to pay the credit, the bank can sell the collateral to settle the credit.

(16) Joint Liability Based. The Joint Liability Based approach can help minimize NPF risk in banking. This approach involves several parties in taking credit, so that no one party is burdened with all the responsibility for credit payments. In this approach, several parties are jointly responsible for paying credit, thereby encouraging them to supervise and control each other. This can reduce the risk of default and NPF risk in banks.

(17) Inflation. A high inflation rate can affect the NPF in banking. Inflation can weaken people's purchasing power and impact debtors' ability to pay credit. In addition, inflation can increase bank operational costs, thereby reducing profitability and the bank's ability to handle NPF.

(18) Initial Public Offering /IPO. IPO can affect NPF in banking. IPO is the process of selling company shares to the public to obtain capital. If banks obtain additional capital through an IPO, banks can expand credit provision and minimize NPF risk. However, if banks experience difficulty in selling shares at the IPO, this can reduce the banking ability to handle NPF risk.

(19) Intellectual Capital. Intellectual capital can help banks to improve the quality of services and products and minimize NPF risk. Intellectual capital is intellectual capital owned by a company such as employee knowledge, experience and expertise. By having intellectual With strong capital, banks can strengthen risk management systems and optimize credit processes so as to minimize NPF risk.

(20) Islamic Prudential Banking Concept. The Islamic Prudential Banking Concept can influence the NPF in sharia banking. This concept refers to sharia principles in managing credit risk and risk management. In this concept, Islamic banking applies a prudential approach in determining credit policies and minimizing NPF risk. These principles include the principles of prudence, fairness and transparency.

(21) Problematic credit. Problematic credit is credit that the customer cannot pay off. Problematic credit can be a cause of NPF in banking. The more non-performing loans a bank has, the higher the risk of NPF occurrence. Problematic credit can be caused by various factors such as creditor quality, economic factors, and other factors.

(22) Managerial ownership. Managerial ownership can influence NPF in banking. If managerial ownership in banking is high, then banking management tends to pay more attention to credit quality and implement a better risk management system. This can help reduce the risk of NPF.

(23) Institutional ownership. Institutional ownership can influence NPF in banking. If institutional ownership in banks is high, then banks tend to be more stable and have better access to resources. This can help banks reduce NPF risk and optimize profitability.

(24) Loan Loss Provision /LLP. Loan Loss Provision (LLP) is a reserve created by banks to cover possible losses due to NPF. LLP can affect NPF in banking. If the LLP owned by a bank is high, then the bank has sufficient reserves to handle NPF. However, if the LLP owned by banks is low, then banks may experience difficulties in handling NPF and this will have an impact on banking profitability.

(25) Profit sharing margin. Profit sharing margin or profit sharing margin is part of the profits obtained by Islamic banks from financing. The profit sharing margin can affect the NPF in sharia banking because the higher the profit sharing margin provided, the higher the NPF risk in sharia banking. This is because the higher the profit sharing margin, the higher the financing costs that must be paid by customers, so the higher the risk of customers experiencing difficulties in paying installments.

(26) Exchange rate/exchange rate. The exchange rate or exchange rate can affect the NPF in sharia banking. Changes in exchange rates can affect the quality of creditors and customers' ability to pay installments. If there is a decline in the exchange rate, customers who have debts in foreign currency will have difficulty paying installments, thereby increasing NPF risk.

(27) Sharia business financing operations. Sharia business financing operations can affect the NPF in sharia banking. Sharia business financing operations include selecting the quality of creditors, selecting the right type of financing, and implementing a good risk management system. If sharia business financing operations are carried out well, NPF risk can be reduced.

(28) Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing. Sharia financing consists of several types, including Murabahah, Mudharabah, and Musyarakah. These types of sharia financing can affect the NPF in sharia banking. Murabahah financing has lower risks compared to Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing. This is because Murabahah financing uses concrete assets as collateral, while Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing is more risk-sharing between the bank and the customer. If Islamic banks provide too much Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing, the NPF risk will increase.

(29) MSME Financing. MSME financing can affect NPF in banking. MSMEs tend to have higher credit risk compared to corporate credit, due to their small business size and limited access to financial resources. Therefore, banks must carry out careful creditworthiness evaluations before providing financing to MSMEs. If banks provide financing to MSMEs carefully, NPF risk can be reduced.

(30) Implementation of Early Warning System /EWS. Implementing EWS can help banks identify NPF risks at an early stage and take appropriate preventive measures. EWS can help banks monitor the quality of creditors and detect signs of financial difficulties in customers. Thus, banks can take appropriate action to prevent NPF.

(31) Role of Account Officer /AO. AO is the spearhead in carrying out creditor activities in banking. AO is responsible for evaluating creditor eligibility before providing financing. AO is also tasked with monitoring the quality of creditors and taking appropriate action if there are signs of financial difficulties among customers. If AO does its job well, the NPF risk can be reduced.

(32) The role of oversight of financing internal audit. Supervision of financing internal audits can help banks ensure that the risk management and internal control systems are running well. Internal audits can help banks identify weaknesses in financing systems and procedures. In this way, banks can make continuous improvements and improvements to existing financing systems and procedures, so as to prevent NPF.

(33) The role of financing monitoring. Monitoring financing can influence NPF risk in banking. Careful and regular monitoring of customers who have been provided with financing can help banks identify signs of financial difficulties in customers. Thus, banks can immediately take appropriate preventive measures and reduce NPF risk.

(34) Role of the Board of Directors. The Board of Directors is responsible for strategic decision making and general control of the bank. Good leadership from the Board of Directors can influence the effectiveness of the bank's risk management and internal control. If the Board of Directors carries out its duties well, the NPF risk can be reduced.

(35) Role of the Sharia Supervisory Board. The Sharia Supervisory Board has the responsibility to ensure that the bank's activities comply with sharia principles and Islamic law. The Sharia Supervisory Board is also responsible for ensuring that the bank has an effective risk management and internal control system. If the Sharia Supervisory Board carries out its duties well, the NPF risk can be reduced.

(36) Role of the Independent Board of Commissioners. The Independent Board of Commissioners has the responsibility to provide independent and critical oversight of company policies and practices. The Independent Board of Commissioners is also responsible for ensuring that the bank has an effective risk management and internal control system. If the Independent Board of Commissioners carries out its duties well, the NPF risk can be reduced.

(37) Economic growth. Economic growth can influence NPF risk in banking. When economic growth is good, the opportunity for customers to repay their financing will increase. Conversely, when economic growth is slow, the NPF risk in banking can increase.

(38) Profit Sharing Ratio /PSR. Profit Sharing Ratio is the profit sharing ratio between the bank and customers. A low ratio can reduce NPF risk in banking, because the bank will receive a smaller share of profits but still receive financing costs and administrative costs. In this case, customers will be more motivated to repay their financing because they will get a larger share of the profits.

(39) Loss sharing financing return ratio divided by total financing return. This ratio can affect NPF risk in banking if the bank uses the loss sharing financing method. A high ratio indicates that the bank has taken greater risks and if a loss occurs, the bank will bear a greater share of the loss. Therefore, this ratio must be carefully monitored and kept at a reasonable level to reduce NPF risk.

(40) Ratio Financing. Ratio Financing is the ratio between financing provided by the bank and deposits received by the bank. A high ratio indicates that the bank has provided more financing compared to the deposits received. This can increase the NPF risk in banking because banks can experience difficulties in fulfilling payment obligations to their customers if large deposits are withdrawn.

(41) Zakat Performing Ratio /ZPR. ZPR is the ratio between zakat funds used to provide financing to customers in need and total bank financing. A high

ZPR can help reduce NPF risk in banking because it helps customers who need to be able to repay their credit. However, the effect depends on the size of the ZPR and how good the zakat distribution mechanism is.

(42) Financial Services Authority Regulation No. 11/POJK.03/2020. This regulation provides guidelines for banks in carrying out financing restructuring. Financing restructuring can help reduce NPF risk in banks by providing alternative solutions for customers who experience difficulty in repaying their financing. In this case, banks will be more motivated to carry out financing restructuring in order to reduce NPF risk.

(43) Financing restructuring. Financing restructuring is an alternative solution provided by banks to customers who have difficulty paying back their financing. In this case, the bank will work together with customers to find the best solution so that customers can repay their financing without having to pose a greater NPF risk for the bank.

(44) Fines imposed on customers. Fines can be an alternative for banks to take action against customers who do not fulfill their payment obligations at the specified time. In this case, fines can be a substitute for increasing NPF risk in banking. Therefore, banks will be more motivated to impose fines on customers who do not fulfill their payment obligations.

(45) Bank Indonesia/SWBI Wadiah Certificate. The influence of Bank Indonesia wadiah certificates on NPF in banking is not very significant, because BI wadiah certificates are actually only an instrument to maintain customer trust and are not directly related to credit quality and NPF.

(46) Socio-economic. The socio-economic level of society can influence the NPF in banking. Customers' inability to repay credit can be caused by social factors such as unemployment, poverty and economic instability.

(47) Murabahah margin level. The margin level in Murabahah type financing can affect the NPF in banking. If the margin offered is too low, it can cause a decline in credit quality and increase NPF risk.

(48) Level of fund distribution. Uncontrolled distribution of funds can increase NPF risk in banks. Therefore, there needs to be strict supervision in the distribution of funds in order to minimize NPF risk.

(49) Company size. Company size can influence NPF in banking. Larger companies tend to have greater resources to manage credit risk and minimize NPF risk.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Non-Performing Financing (NPF) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2009 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 576 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the NPF ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 4 clusters and 178 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 61 topics, cluster 2 consists of 59 topics, cluster 3 consists of 38 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 20 topics. Third, based on mapping studies Library Research, there are 32 topics related to the influence of the NPF ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Operating Costs Operating Income/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Debt Financing, Earnings Management, Efficiency, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, Financial Sustainability Ratio /FSR, Financing of Natural Uncertainty Contract

/NUC, zakat compliance, financial performance, company profit, Murabahah margin, Net Operating Margin /NOM, company value, distribution of Murabahah, Mudharabah, Musyarakah financing, primary, secondary and tertiary economic sector financing, development sharia banking, determination of profit sharing ratio, financing portion, asset growth, fraud disclosure, Profit Expense Ratio /PER, Return On Assets /ROA, Return On Equity /ROE, Return for Deposit /RfD Result, stock returns, liquidity risk, banking stability sharia, level of profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits, level of liquidity, total assets, and volume of financing.

Furthermore, there are 49 topics related to the determinants of the NPF ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: allocation of zakat funds, Operational Costs Operational Income/BOPO, BI rate, Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Current Ratio, Covid-19, Third Party Funds/ DPK, sectoral financing diversification, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR, financing growth, Financing Scheme Effect, Gross Domestic Product /GDP, Good Corporate Governance /GCG, hybrid contracts for restructuring, Guarantees, joint liability based, inflation, Initial Public Offering /IPO, intellectual capital, Islamic prudential banking concept, non-performing loans, managerial ownership, Loan Loss Provision/LLP, profit sharing margin, exchange rate, sharia business financing operations, Murabahah financing, MSME financing, implementation of the Early Warning System/EWS, role of Accounts Officer/AO, role of monitoring internal audit of financing, role of financing monitoring, role of the Board of Directors, role of the Sharia Supervisory Board, role of the Independent Board of Commissioners, economic growth, Profit Sharing Ratio/PSR, loss sharing financing return ratio divided by total financing return, Financing Ratio, Financial Services Authority regulation no. 11/POJK.03/2020, financing restructuring, fines for customers, Bank Indonesia/SWBI Wadiah Certificates, socio-economics, Murabahah margin levels, fund distribution levels, company size, and Zakat Performing Ratio/ZPR.

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